

Developmental Neuromorphic Learning for Autonomous & Adaptive Space Exploration with Hierarchical SNN Integration

Rithvik Suren
Academy of Aerospace and Engineering
Jeffrey S. Katz

Senior Member, IEEE; Connecticut District VP, Yale Science and Engineering Association, Retired CTO of IBM Energy & Utilities Industry

1 Abstract

Space exploration demands adaptive, efficient systems operating under strict hardware constraints¹. Current AI-driven rovers, such as NASA’s Perseverance, are limited by SWaP (size, weight, and power), radiation-hardened components, and onboard processing latency². This research presents a lightweight developmental neuromorphic framework that learns and adapts through experience, integrating Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) with hierarchical reinforcement learning for autonomous space exploration, targeting robustness, efficiency and performance goals. This approach addresses power efficiency and radiation robustness through event-driven computation mimicking biological neural processing³. Testing on Raspberry Pi hardware using Mars terrain data from NASA’s MOLA dataset demonstrated 30× reduction in CPU time with balanced 11% RAM/CPU utilization compared to traditional algorithms (96.3% RAM, 6% CPU). Statistical validation via t-test ($t \approx 7$, $p < 0.01$) confirmed superior policy formation and decision-making performance. Radiation simulation and Gaussian noise perturbation (0-20%) validated system robustness goals. These results highlight gains in adaptability and efficiency, for protection of compact AI for planetary missions.

2 Methods

Terrain Environment: NASA’s Mars Orbiter Laser Altimeter (MOLA) dataset was utilized for terrain curation, containing 717 million Martian surface measurements. A composite diversity score ($C = \sum(x_j \cdot w_j)$) was computed using weighted terrain metrics including elevation range, roughness, and spatial coverage ($w=0.2, 0.25, 0.15$), identifying robust training regions. PyBullet simulation engine generated realistic height-mapped environments scaled for computational constraints.

Neuromorphic Architecture: The hierarchical framework employs two-level policy decomposition. High-level (HL) policy manages control planning through sparse navigation graphs, demonstrated 50% computational runtime reduction previously⁴. Low-level (LL) policy controls locomotion using SNN-based Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

with regularizations for joint torque, acceleration, and series elasticity modeling Series Elastic Actuators (SEAs)⁵.

Robustness Testing: Gaussian noise injection (0-20%) simulated radiation-induced sensor interference. t-SNE analysis visualized action-space clustering evolution during training. Welch’s t-test compared policy formation metrics between SNN-PPO and conventional ANN-PPO. Temperature and radiation modeling in Fusion360 validated long-term hardware viability.

Hardware Implementation: Raspberry Pi 4B simulated resource-constrained rover conditions. Two computational frameworks were compared: In-Memory Parallel (IMP) as control and Neuromorphic Processing (NP) as experimental model. Performance metrics included CPU time, usage, and RAM usage using Python’s time and tracemalloc libraries.

3 Preliminary Results

The neuromorphic framework achieved significant performance improvements across multiple metrics. Processing speed increased 30-fold (10ms vs 300ms) while maintaining superior resource efficiency with balanced 11% RAM/CPU utilization compared to IMP’s unbalanced 96.3% RAM and 6% CPU usage.

Noise robustness testing revealed superior adaptability, with SNN-PPO maintaining reward acquisition up to 13.5 compared to ANN-PPO’s maximum (10) under identical Gaussian noise conditions. The delayed failure onset demonstrates enhanced fault tolerance for autonomous operation in the unpredictable Martian environment.

t-SNE visualization revealed structured action-space clustering in SNN-PPO with minimal outliers, indicating rapid and developmental policy formation, and efficient decision convergence. Statistical validation confirmed a significant difference in clustering quality (silhouette scoring) with p -value ≈ 0.004 and t -statistic ≈ 7.44 , exceeding standard thresholds. Temperature & heat transfer stability across 600-second intervals under simulated Martian atmospheric conditions indicated consistent rover operation, confirming thermal robustness for extended mission durations. The preliminary results demonstrate the framework’s potential to address critical limitations in space exploration systems, paving the way for advanced autonomous, adaptive rovers capable of self-maintenance and independent operation on Mars and beyond.

ration planner for space applications. IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters.

⁵Pratt, G.A., & Williamson, M.M. Series elastic actuators. Proceedings 1995 IEEE/RSJ International Conference.

¹Edwards, S. (2017). Limits to rover miniaturisation and their implications for solar system exploration.

²Verma, V., et al. (2023). Autonomous robotics is driving Perseverance rover’s progress on Mars. Science Robotics, 8(80).

³Naoukin, J., et al. (2023). A survey examining neuromorphic architecture in space and challenges from radiation. ArXiv.

⁴Varadharajan, V.S., & Beltrame, G. (2025). A multi-robot explo-